

**THE IMPACT OF CLINICAL USE OF ELECTRONIC HEALTH RECORDS
(EHR) ON THE QUALITY OF MEDICAL CARE IN FEDERAL TEACHING
HOSPITAL, IDO-EKITI, NIGERIA**

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Nigeria**

Abstract

Objective: Quality medical care is the extent to which medical care services meet or possess the inherent potential of meeting the desired health outcome. The importance of quality medical care to humanity cannot be over-emphasized. This is because human wellbeing, productivity and qualitative life largely depend on it. Medical care services in Low-and-Middle-Income Countries, including Nigeria, has been in a worrisome state for decades and everyone yearns for better quality. As part of the factors that impact quality medical care, the clinical use of EHR is discussed in literature as a possible contributor. Examining the veracity of the assertion, this study therefore used empirical data to determine the impact of the clinical use of EHR on quality medical care in the Federal Teaching Hospital, Ido-Ekiti, Nigeria.

Method: Quantitative research method and survey design was adopted for the study. The population of the study is 296 medical doctors at Federal Teaching Hospital, Ido-Ekiti, Nigeria. Sample size is 169 obtained from the Krejcie and Morgan sample size table. Systematic sampling technique was used to select participants for the study. Data was collected using validated structured questionnaire with Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient score of 0.98 and 0.96 for clinical use of EHR and quality of medical care respectively.

Findings: Results from the study showed that clinical use of EHR has a positive and significant impact on the quality of medical care with a P value less than 0.05. ($p = 0.000$, $B = 0.74$, $Adj. R^2 = 0.55$, $F_{1,163} = 202.57$). The findings further revealed that the quality of medical care in the

hospital is good (Mean =3.99) while the extent of clinical use of EHR is to a high extent (Mean = 4.10) on the scale.

Conclusion: The study concluded that the clinical use of EHR has positive and significant impact on the quality of medical care in the hospital. It is suggested that all hospitals within and outside Nigeria should invest more in the clinical use of EHR in order to achieve the desired very high-quality medical care across board. Meanwhile, the Federal Teaching Hospital Ido-Ekiti should sustain the clinical use of EHR in order to maintain and possibly improve upon the present quality of medical care in the hospital.

Keywords: Electronic Health Records, Federal Teaching Hospital, Healthcare, Ido-Ekiti, Nigeria, Quality medical care.

Introduction:

Quality medical care is the extent to which the medical care services rendered to individuals and the population meet or increase the likelihood of meeting the desired health outcome (WHO, 2022). This definition has been widely adopted in literature in understanding the concept of quality medical care. Two things are clearly established in the definition – medical care services and desired health outcome. Good medical services is assumed to translate into satisfactory health outcome for the consumers and vice-versa. Since the predictor of a satisfactory health outcome is the medical care service, then the focus on the constituents of quality medical care service.

According to Donabedian (2003), a quality medical care services is achieved through an interplay of healthcare structure and process that results in health outcome that is satisfactory. The structure refers to the array of resources, both tangible and intangibles, provided and mobilized for the production of healthcare services. These resources include physical buildings, access roads, electricity, internet and intranet connections, portable water supply, staff and staff welfare, equipment, machines, standard operation procedures, methods, motivation factors as well as drug and consumables. The process are the activities involved in translating the structure to services for the patients and clients. These activities include booking of appointments,

documenting patients, clinical consultations, clinical examinations, medical and surgical procedures, communications, laboratory and radiology investigations, pharmaceutical services, counselling, billing and reporting. The outcome is the impression of the consumer on the standard of the services received. This is informed by the restoration of health or meeting of the health need, commendations, lack of complaints, patronage, referral of others, expression of satisfaction, cooperation and goodwill of patients.

This shows clearly that the setting up and deployment of resources for the provision of medical care is not enough. Perhaps more important is the process – the way and manner in which the services are rendered to the patients - that determines patient satisfaction. This argument was authenticated by the findings of the study of Roder-Dewan et al (2019) and Umoke et al (2020) where patients express satisfaction with the medical care services received despite poor structure in place. This could be explained by the way and manner in which the services were rendered to the patient. According to WHO (2020), medical care should be rendered in a way that is safe, efficient, effective, timely, responsive, acceptable and affordable for the desired health outcome to be achieved and patients satisfied.

Safety connotes that the medical care is rendered in a way to prevent harm to patients. This means that all situations that could actually harm or have the potential of harming the patients are proactively controlled. Efficiency relates to the most prudent use of resources in a way void of waste or/and putting undue financial burden on the patient or the state. Similarly, timeliness is the provision of the care within an acceptable time frame void of any delay. Medical care are also expected to be responsive to the needs and requests of the patients and not imposed. Acceptability is the reception of the consumers to the services. This oftentimes is influenced by the culture and social characteristics of the people or society. Affordability relates to the cost of the services and the financial strength of the consumers. When the quality of medical care is improved, it has the capacity of preventing deaths and incapacitation, enhancing productivity

as well as promoting quality of life of the people. In the submission of the WHO, quality medical care could prevent 2.5 million deaths arising from cardiovascular diseases, 900,000 fatalities from tuberculosis, 1 million infant mortalities and maternal mortalities could also be reduced by half yearly (WHO, 2022).

Unfortunately, the situation of quality of medical care in Low-and-Middle-Income countries including Nigeria is far from the desired quality and worrisome (Akindele, 2019; Odunaiya, Akinpelu, Ogwu & Aje, 2019; Odetola & Fakorede, 2018; Menizibeya, 2011). According to the recent statistics from the World Health Organization, of the 5.7 – 8.4 million deaths that occur in these countries every year, 60% are due to poor quality medical care while the remaining 40% are caused by non-utilization of the medical system due to accessibility and affordability problems. Similarly, between 1.4 and 1.6 Million Dollars are lost annually in this countries due to loss of productivity arising from poor quality medical services (WHO, 2022).

The use of Electronic Health Records (EHR) has been identified as one of the factors that could help achieve the desired standard of quality medical care (Vest, Unruh, Freedman & Simon (2019); Akindele, 2019; Waithera, Muhia, & Songole, 2017; Odekunle, 2016; Essien & Ntekpere, 2014). EHR transcends just a digital version of paper medical records of patients as it now provides vital clinical functions that help clinicians make good clinical decisions that promote quality medical care (Odekunle, 2016). Apart from the clinical functions of EHR (which is the focus of this study), the technology is also applied for administrative functions such as billing of patients, scheduling of hospital appointments, tracking of patient attendance, reporting, and integrated communication (AHIMA, 2007).

The clinical use of EHR involves the application EHR solution to create, store and access medical information (data repository use) for the treatment of patients in the clinics. Here physician documentations (PD) are generated, warehoused and accessed for authorized use at

the different clinical service points within the hospital. Also, the clinical use of EHR include laboratory and radiology result management which allows providers to order laboratory investigations, document results as well as access and use the results for patients' clinical management. This is also known as the Computerized Provider Order Entry (CPOE) management. Furthermore, the clinical use of EHR involves the deployment of an artificial intelligence embedded in the solution to help care providers make good clinical decisions that promote the quality of medical care rendered to patients. This is known as Computerized Decision Support System (CDSS). The CDSS helps clinical decisions on diagnosing and prescribing in a way that is knowledge-based and beneficial to the patient.

According to Akindele and Soyemi (2021), a haphazard application of EHR may be counterproductive. EHR deployment and use must be strategic in order to achieve the desired effect. Meaningful use of EHR requires the standardization of the technology as well as its proper and purposeful deployment. While focusing on the use of EHR for the purpose of achieving a better quality of medical care, strategic application of the technology could mean its clinical use. However, this is based on the assumption that the clinical use of EHR could help improve quality of medical care. This assumption that the clinical use of EHR could bring about a better quality of medical care need to be tested to confirm or refute the claim, hence this study. The study is aimed at determining the:

1. Quality of medical care in the Federal Teaching Hospital, Ido-Ekiti, Nigeria;
2. Extent of use of EHR in the Federal Teaching Hospital, Ido-Ekiti, Nigeria; and
3. Influence of the clinical use of EHR on quality of medical care in the Federal Teaching Hospital, Ido-Ekiti, Nigeria.

Method:

The study adopted a survey research design based on post-positivist epistemology. The study population is 296 medical doctors at Federal Teaching Hospital, Ido-Ekiti, Nigeria. Using the Krejcie and Morgan sample size table, a sample size of 169 was obtained. Systematic sampling technique was used to select participants for the study. The instrument for data collection was adapted questionnaire which was subjected to validity and reliability tests before use. Face and content validity was done by peers and other researchers. A Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient score of the clinical use of Electronic Health Records is 0.978 while quality of medical care accounted for 0.956. With the general rule that 0.70 and above are considered to be adequate, these scores suggest a high level of internal coherence among the survey items used to measure the two key constructs of the study.

A 98% (n = 165) return rate was achieved as 165 copies of the questionnaire were returned and suitable for analysis. Data was analysed using the Statistical Product and Services Solution (SPSS) version 21 with descriptive and inferential statistical output.

The study was carried out with strict adherence to ethical considerations. Ethical approval was obtained from the research ethics committee with an approval number BUHREC286. Also, consent forms were issued to participants and were given time to review the consent and decide on their participation or otherwise in the study. Participants were also guaranteed anonymity and confidentiality of data given. Data was used for research purpose only and secured in locked steel cabinet as well as passworded personal computers.

Findings:

Out of the 165 medical doctors surveyed, 47.3% (n=78) are male while 52.7% (n=87) are female. 70.9% (n=117) of the doctors are within the ages of 31-45 years with 72.2% (n=119) having less than 11 years clinical experience. Most 62.4% (n=103) of them are also medical officers and the least 1.2% (n=2) are medical doctors on internship.

A Decision Rule of 1.0 - 1.7 = Very Poor; 1.8 - 2.5 = Poor; 2.6 - 3.3 = Fair; 3.4 - 4.1 = Good; 4.2-5.0 = Very Good was developed for the study and the quality of medical care services has an overall mean of 3.99 on the scale. This means that the quality of medical care in Federal Teaching Hospital, Ido-Ekiti is ‘good’.

Similarly, with a decision rule of 1.0 - 1.7 = Very Low Extent; 1.8 - 2.5 = Low Extent; 2.6 - 3.3 = Moderate Extent; 3.4 - 4.1 = High Extent; 4.2-5.0 = Very High Extent, the extent of clinical use of EHR has an overall mean of 4.10. This means that the extent of use of EHR in Federal Teaching Hospital, Ido-Ekiti is ‘High Extent’

Lastly, clinical use of EHR positively and significantly influenced quality of medical care with a P value of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$) in Federal Teaching Hospital, Ido-Ekiti. This shows that there is a positive and significant influence of clinical use of EHR on quality medical care in Federal Teaching Hospital, Ido-Ekiti.

Table 1: The impact of clinical use of EHR on quality of medical care in Federal Teaching Hospital, Ido-Ekiti.

Variables	Beta (β)	T	Sig.	R ²	Adj. R ²	F	p
(Constant)		15.853	.000	.554	.551	202.567	0.000
Clinical use of EHR	.744	14.233	.000				
Dependent Variable: Quality of Medical Care Predictor: Clinical use of EHR DF (F-Statistic) = 1, 163 DF (T-Statistic) = 164							

Discussion of findings

The quality of medical care in the Federal Teaching Hospital, Ido-Ekiti was found to be good. This finding is at variance with the results from many other empirical studies such as those of Ameh, et al (2020); Odunaiya, Akinpelu, Ogwu and Aje (2019) as well as that of Odetola and Fakorede (2018) which found the quality of medical care in Nigeria’s hospitals to be poor. Nevertheless, the finding agrees with the results from the works of Umoke, et al. (2020) and Andoh-Adjei, et al. (2018) which discovered that the quality of medical care in Nigeria’s hospitals is good. This finding may have shown that the ongoing investments of government and concerned non-governmental organization in the healthcare system is yielding a positive result and patients are getting satisfied with the services they receive in the hospitals.

Similarly, the clinical use of EHR in Federal Teaching Hospital, Ido-Ekiti is to a high extent. This is agreement with the fact that ICT is already ubiquitous and its deliverables being appreciated and appropriated by most professionals in the course of their services. Also, the medical doctors are literates and skilled professionals who are disposed to continuous personal and professional development. This disposition may have put a demand of ICT appreciation and use on them over the years thereby informing their use of the EHR technology. This may be in addition to the deliberate efforts of the Management of the hospital to encourage the use of EHR in the hospital.

Finally, the study found a positive and significant relationship between the clinical use of EHR and the quality of medical care in Federal Teaching Hospital, Ido-Ekiti. This finding is in agreement with that of Blumer and Primmer (2019) as well as that of Kennedy and Yaldren (2017). This shows that the more the clinical use of EHR, the better the quality of medical care rendered to patients as the clinical use of EHR accounted for 55.1% of the variation in the quality of medical care.

Conclusion:

This study became necessary as part of the global efforts to provide quality medical care to all for the benefit of mankind. The veracity of the claim in literature that clinical use of EHR could contribute to a high quality medical care was subjected to empirical analysis and the result was in the affirmative of the claim. The high quality medical care discovered in the study area may also be connected to the high extent of clinical use of EHR in the hospital. In view of this, it is important to suggest that all other hospitals in the country, and of course globally, should invest more in the clinical use of EHR in order to achieve the desired very high quality medical care across board. Meanwhile, the Federal Teaching Hospital Ido-Ekiti should also sustain the clinical use of EHR in order to maintain and possibly improve upon the present quality of medical care in the hospital.

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